

Suggested Educational Program based on the Multiple Intelligences Theory and its Influence in the Development of Communication Skills and Retention of Learning Influence in Kindergartens (KG2)

Odeh Suleiman Murad, Raed Ahmad Al-Kriemeen, Walled Mohammad Al-Shatarat

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Suggested, Educational Program, Multiple Intelligences Communication Skills, Retention of Learning Influence</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5103835</p>	<p><i>The theory of multiple intelligences presented a modern image of the human intelligence through which tutorials (educational programs) could be provided. Consistent with the various age stages, this theory calls for the uniqueness of education and construction of curriculum, depending on the investment on strengths and the development and enhancement of these aspects, and in addition to treat the weaknesses through the educational experiences one adapts, and all of this is according to individual educational plans. The current study aimed to reveal the efficiency of a suggested educational program based on the theory of multiple intelligences and its influence in the development of communication skills and retention of learning influence in kindergartens (KG2). The study sample was composed of two groups, the experimental and control group, which contained 185 male and female children in each group. The study tool was represented by an achievement test to measure the communication skills. After investigating its reliability and validity, it was applied to the two groups of study, before and after the program. Findings have shown the effectiveness of the suggested educational program in developing communication skills and retention of learning influence.</i></p>

Introduction

Today, we live in an era of discoveries, inventions and theories of all the sciences, especially in the field of technology. And because of the huge amount of knowledge and information through which the learners pass, they do not have the ability to maintain information in their memories for long. In addition, since the individual is important to build and lead society, we must take care in developing his thought and intelligence as he is a mental, physical and emotional creature. This can happen through modern educational teaching methods which highlight the places of multiple intelligences in the learner. We need to utilize and invest these intelligences and empower them to use research methods, discovery and innovation effectively to keep up with time changes (Murad, 2021b).

We must take care of human thought, abilities and intelligence, and not look at human intelligence with the old monolithic view which looked at intelligence as a unified mental entity and consideration the human intelligences as relatively independent of each other. Gardener (1983) sees that traditional theories of intelligence do not appreciate properly human intelligence as they are based on traditional intelligence tests, and these depends little on mental abilities, and besides, they are not fair since it requires the individuals to solve problems only linguistically or verbally. Furthermore, the psychologists differed in their views of intelligence. As a result, it has many definitions, concepts, and theories because of the ambiguity of the concept of intelligence and the difficulty in accuracy determining what it is (Murad, 2021a). Moreover, the multiple intelligences theory of Gardener is considered the most important, as it attempted to provide practical illustrations of the mental activity, logically and systematically according to its components, limitations and factors from which it was composed of. This theory is still common till date and it has entered in the methods of learning and educational process development and it significantly concentrates on the learner's personality (Afanah & Al-khazendar, 2007).

Gardener pointed that the intelligences are important in the knowledge of learning methods and teaching strategies, in which they contribute in developing the intellectual skills and abilities of the individual. Among these skills are the skills of linguistic communication. It facilitates acquiring of new knowledge which is stored in the long-term memory in the shape of knowledge constructions, to recall what is needed when faced with unfamiliar or vague situations that hinders the comprehension process of the individual (Murad, 2021a). Gardener utilizes these skills and experiences to communicate with others and to solve many types of problems and among these is the problem related to the four communication skills (listening, conversation, reading and writing) (Gardener, 1993).

Hence, we find that the multiple intelligences theory attempts to change the view of the individuals on their general intelligence by evaluating their logical and verbal abilities and by looking at them as the persons who own various differentiated abilities. Teaching methods have to be consistent with these abilities through concentration on strength points and developing on these points (Murad, 2018). Studying the multiple intelligences helps to guide every individual to the job that suits their abilities, energies and capabilities and is expected to succeed in it. So, if the suitable intelligence type is used correctly, many problems can be solved. Every individual is capable of developing their intelligences to a reasonable level of performance. He could develop his learning strategies and adapt to various situations when the conditions of learning and enrichment are available for him in addition to the suitable enhancement and encouragement processes (Al-Khaffaf, 2011).

For that reason, Gardener says that we don't deal with child intelligence in education as the curricula are based on rote memorization, and that the concentration must be on the different activities of the multiple intelligences, so that every child benefits from an activity that suits his intelligence. Kindergartens have received an increased attention in the last few years, and they became the focus of attention for many teachers, specialists, parents and others (Gardener, 1993). This coincided with the increase of scientific research on the human brain, represented in many theories. Researches seek to find an illustration of these problems, developing methods and educational means. Additionally, to amend the educational environments that could meet the unique needs of this sensitive age and prepare professional, competent teachers and trainers. Moreover, Gardener (1993) explained that multiple intelligences are mental skills necessary for the development of individuals, that there is a difference among the individuals according to their skills and abilities, and this refers to the available intelligences types for individuals and the rate of activating each of them (Jaber, 2003).

Language is the vessel of thought and the title of authentic culture. It is the tool of receiving knowledge, thinking, expression, communication and understanding among people. In addition, language is the symbol of the will to live, the man's window to the future and the symbol of his embodiment. There is no doubt that the contemporary life includes many forms of participation and activation, along with exchange of views, thoughts and information with others or practicing various communication types inside or outside the school. It requires from the providers of Arabic language curricula and its teaching methods more attention in basic communication skills, according to the logical order of the basic language skills system: listening, conversation, reading and writing and its behavioral indicators. Also, developing them for children via live and natural situations in which the child performs his role as a member of a democratic society able to present himself and his thoughts to the world, to express himself including what he participates and submits in, in order to interact and communicate with others (Naser & Al-Abbadi, 2005).

The communication skills with others and interaction with them is one of the most important functions of language. It is a tool and means through which the individual understands and connects with his group in order to achieve his goals and needs. Moreover, it forms a main factor in the individual knowledge regarding surrounding events. Also, the linguistic skills are considered as a basic precondition to develop other skills whether in the kindergartens or other following stages. As the language is the key to communicate with others, it is an important tool on which linguistic construction of humans depends on.

In the field, researchers have observed that the female kindergarten teachers used the traditional methods in educating children. The idea of the research came from the necessity of creating an educational program based on multiple intelligences theory and then testing its influence on the dependent study variables and concentrated on the development of communication skills, achievement level and maintenance of learning influence on the sample of children from kindergartens.

Multiple Intelligences

Intelligences related to the study and tackled by Gardner's theory could be described as following:

Verbal linguistic intelligence

It is the ability to use written or uttered language and the ability to learn this language effectively, then using it to achieve specific purposes, utilizing the language orally or in writing whether it is the mother tongue or any other languages (Hussein, 2003; Armstrong, 2006). The researchers view that linguistic intelligence is defined as individual ability to use words, sentences, and language orally or in writing in a good manner in which he could deliver the message and correct pronunciation with vocalizing to others.

Logical mathematical intelligence

It is the individual ability to deal with the conclusions and their effects. Moreover, it is an intelligence that is based on logic and mathematical guesswork and to check the problems and issues systematically (Jaber, 2003). The researchers also are of the view that the logical mathematical intelligence means the individual ability to use numbers and dealing with them, to illustrate the relations and problems effectively, and the ability of good understanding of cause and effect. It also deals with complex mathematical operations and problems.

Visual spatial intelligence

It is the ability to recognize the visual spatial world accurately through visual discrimination skills, visual expression, spatial reasoning, recognizing three-dimensional images, artistic creativity based on fertile imagination in creating mental images and dealing with them in order to solve problems or conducting

amendments (Awad, 2011). The researchers define the visual spatial intelligence as the individual ability to judge things and events through sight, whether it is an image, verbal or non-verbal expression, symbols or imagining images and words and expressing them through drawing.

The theory of multiple intelligences is based on a number of principles represented by: diverse and multiple intelligences subjected to development and change. The intelligence is very advanced in some types, moderate in some others and relatively undeveloped in the rest of the types (Gardener, 1993).

Moreover, every person owns a unique mixture of diverse and active intelligences groups, the intelligences differ according to the growth inside every individual and in terms of how each is sufficiently utilized to determine the suitable strategy to achieve his goals and purposes. It is possible to know, determine and measure the multiple intelligences, and some intelligences contributes to the enhancement and development of other intelligences, if provided with appropriate encouragement, information, motive and training (Al-Salti, 2004). Furthermore, it is important to know that all types of intelligence are vital and dynamic, it is impossible to differentiate or observe specific intelligences itself, and individuals are treated according to the abilities, capabilities, readiness and interests they own (Afanah & Al-Khazendar, 2009; Karen, 2010).

From what has been mentioned above, we conclude that most people could develop every intelligence to get it to the appropriate level of efficiency. Multiple intelligences are not available in one individual, but they are distributed among individuals in which one person has more than one intelligence and to develop one of these intelligences may contribute in the development of the rest of the intelligences.

Communication Skills

Listening skill

Listening is considered a main linguistic art among the four language arts which are listening, conversation, reading and writing. Moreover, it is the primary language art that a child deals with and through which he starts his external relations with the surroundings. So, the listening skills begins to grow before the other skill, the listener child gives special interest to the speaker and intended attention to what sounds and voices the ear receives (Tuaimah & Manna', 2001). The educators have divided listening skills into four main parts: understanding and its accuracy, comprehension, concentration and tasting aesthetic values and understanding (Al-Assaf & Abu-Latifa, 2009).

Conversation skill

It is defined as a debate, or a free, automatic discussion conducted between two individuals or more on specific topic, and it forms a social communication tool according to a system of relations and symbols to be between humans. Furthermore, conversation skill includes mental and performance processes conducted by the individual through oral translation (verbal, semantic and grammatical) of what is in the speaker's mind, to express his thoughts, feelings, passions, trends, meanings, events or views to others in a way that he finds favors from others (Tuaimah & Manaa', 2001; Al-Esawi, Musa & Al-Sherawi, 2005). The most important teaching method used to help children to the performance quality conversations are the following: Discussion and debate, exchanging information, description, re-narration and role-playing.

Reading skill

It is a method of the intellectual activity and is an indispensable skill in any educational content. Reading is also considered as a communicative tool and language between the reader and written text; because the recent concepts of reading consider it as a communication activity between the author and the reader through written material (Al-Tahhan, 2003). The ways in which it is used in education, reading is classified into: the synthetic method, which includes (the phonemic, orthographic and syllabic method), the analytical method that includes (word method, sentence or utterance method and story method), the combinative method (analytical, synthetic) which contains a set of steps like the preparation stage for reading, the words and sentences introduction stage, synthesis, analysis and editing stage, analysis of the sentence into words and finally, phonemic editing (Abu-Maghli & Salameh, 2005).

Writing skill

It is a skill of expression, communication and a learning tool through which the child transmits his thoughts, feelings and views for others. It is a kinematic promoted skill, developed and enhanced through practicing, whether by writing or through using computer (Mubaideen, 2003).

Writing education concentrates on the child's ability to write correctly and the mastery of handwriting through training, to write the symbols of the known language and develop the ability to express his own ideas clearly and accurately (Al-Assaf & Abu-Latifa, 2009).

By looking at previous literature reviews, the researchers found a number of studies that tackled the variables of the current study and these studies were differentiated in their purposes and one of them is the Al-Zoubi study (2020) which revealed the effectiveness of utilizing Gardener theory in developing verbal and linguistic skills and its reflection on the students' performance. Another one is the Masarrat Study (2016) that revealed the effectiveness of the educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in developing the academic achievement and mathematical thinking, also the learning of influence maintenance for students of the high primary stage. Yet, the Awad study (2011), its findings revealed a difference with statistical

significance in understanding physical concepts because of the teaching strategy based on the multiple intelligences' theory.

The Al-Ahdal study (2009) recommended the necessity to prepare training courses for female teachers, supervisors, and educators to take the benefits of the multiple intelligences' theory in teaching, and the necessity to diversify the teaching methods and educational strategies according to the varied students intelligences. However, the findings of the Onezat study (2006) revealed the effectiveness of utilizing the multiple intelligences theory in teaching students with learning difficulties and disabilities and the impact of this program in enhancing their writing and reading skills. The Bilgin study (2006), aimed to compare between the impacts of teaching application based on the multiple intelligences theory and the traditional methods of teaching Science (Chemistry) based on achievements and trends, for the students of ninth grade. The findings have shown that academic achievement for the students of experimental group was better than of students in the control group. So, the study recommended the importance of training teachers to apply teaching and education based on the multiple intelligences theory.

Furthermore, the Saleh study (2004) had shown the effectiveness of using the multiple intelligence theory as a method and learning tool to develop the mathematical logical intelligence and optical spatial intelligence of the kindergarten students. Also, the effectiveness of activities prepared in developing intelligences for children, represented by mathematical logical intelligence and optical spatial intelligence, the study by Davis (2004) revealed the effectiveness of using the strategies of the multiple intelligences theory in increasing the level of academic achievement for the students of fourth grade in science, resulting in good behavior and increased self-respect.

Low, Nelson, Donnell and Walker's (2001) study have shown the effectiveness of education activities and strategies based on the multiple intelligences' theory in the enhancement of reading and writing skills for a sample of children in pre-school. Findings of post test revealed that the strategies stemming from the multiple intelligences' theory enhance the reading and writing skills of all sample individuals including children with learning difficulties.

The current study differs from previous studies in constructing a suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory and testing its influence in developing the skills of reading, writing, conversation, listening and learning influence maintenance for the students of KG2. As far as the researchers know, this topic has not been addressed in any previous studies with these parameters. Also, all the previous studies findings revealed a clear enhancement in the levels of achievement and learning influence maintenance for their sample individuals, because their teaching methods and educational activities were based on multiple intelligences theory.

Current Study

The problem of the study is summarized as using the approach of multiple intelligences theory and its educational and practical applications in educating children in kindergarten based on the different abilities and potential of each individual. In other words, some of these abilities and potentials could be weak or strong as Al-Waqfi (2003) indicated, that traditional methods are applied without looking at the patterns and strategies of thinking of each individual child. Usually, the concentration is on the linguistic, logical intelligence, neglecting other intelligences and this is because of the concentration on mental activities that are related to mathematical and linguistic abilities, on which the current system of education depends. In addition to the disability of current curricula to utilize the multiple intelligences in development and enhancement of academic achievements that is based on tradition, frequency, copying and rote memorization, which concentrates on the points of weakness, neglects the strength points and its development. Furthermore, the study problem highlights the effectiveness of the suggested educational program based on multiple intelligences theory in the development of communication skills and learning influence maintenance through responding to and answering the following questions:

1. What is the influence of using the suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in the development of communication skills (listening, conversation, reading and writing) for the students of kindergarten (KG2)?

2- What is the influence of using the suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in retention of learning for the students of kindergarten (KG2)?

Aim of the Study

—It is hoped that this study will benefit the kindergarten's curricula planners in adopting the multiple intelligences theory in curricula and developing means, methods and tests in a way that meets the needs and individual differences in learning the children have.

—It could benefit people who are interested in education by making them know the most important concepts and skills of the effective education, and to develop educational skills for female teachers of kindergartens in the light of the multiple intelligences theory through concentration on skills that are weak.

—The suggested educational program could help the female teachers of kindergartens to promote their performance levels and develop their teaching potential.

Limitations:

- Temporal (time) limits: Second academic semester of the year 2018–2019.
- Spatial limits: The study was limited to the Al-Balqa Governorate, especially the city of Al-Salt.
- Participant limits: The students of KG2 in the public and private schools.
- Procedural limits: The findings of the study are determined according to the conditions related to the sample selection, its size, the method of selection, and the study tools in terms of its reliability and validity and to its application conditions.

Methods

The researchers have used the semi-experimental approach, using two groups design (experimental and control) in which the two groups are exposed to a pre-scale then a post-scale, in order to know the influence that the suggested educational program caused in developing the communication skills for the children of the experimental group.

Participants

The study population includes the children of kindergartens (KG2) in Al-salt education directorate, Al-Balqa of the academic year 2018–2019, with a total number of 2457 children. The study sample was limited to 370 male and female children distributed across three kindergartens in which the sample individuals have been divided randomly into two groups (experimental and control), each with 185 children comprising of male and female children as shown in Table (1).

Table 1: The distribution of the study sample according to the gender and kindergarten

kindergarten	Gender	Experimental	Control	Percentage
Al-Eman	Males	46	45	25%
	Females	47	47	25%
Hebatullah	Males	30	31	16%
	Females	32	32	17%
Al-Rayaheen	Males	15	15	8%
	Females	15	15	8%
Total		185	185	100%

Measurement

Achievement test to measure communication skills level (ATMCS)

After the determination of behavioral goals using a number of questions, the researchers prepared paragraphs to measure the behavioral goals whose number was twenty (20) goals. One paragraph for every behavioral goal, including objective tests such as true or false, letters supplement test, matching test and multiple-choice test and every question has five (5) degrees, one (1) degree is given for every branch of question if the response is correct and zero (0) degree if the response is false.

Validity of ATMCS

The items of the achievement test were presented to a group of experts and specialists in teaching the Arabic language. The specialization of measurement and assessment by the teachers of kindergartens, to reach the final draft of the test paragraphs, scientific investigation of their validity, their linguistic integrity and the checking the accuracy of the suggested alternatives was carried out. Furthermore, the researchers have considered the amendments recommended by the arbitrators after all experts agreed on the final version of the achievement test with an 85% agreement.

Reliability of ATMCS

To achieve that, the test was applied to an exploratory sample of 30 children selected from the study population and from outside this sample in order to calculate the reliability coefficient of the achievement test through repetition between the pre-scale and post-scale with a 15 day interval, in which the Pearson correlation coefficient of the basic communication of the pre and post-test was 0.82, and this coefficient is considered as a good indicator for the test reliability as illustrated in Table (2).

Table 2: Reliability coefficients of the multiple development intelligences scales through Test-Retest method

No.	Multiple development intelligences	Test-Retest coefficients
1	Verbal/linguistic intelligences	0.83
2	Mathematical logical intelligences	0.85
3	Spatial intelligences	0.80

Moreover, difficulty coefficients of the test items were calculated in which they ranged between (0.75-0.35) in addition to the coefficients that distinguish items, in which they ranged between (0.32-0.06).

Suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory (SEPBMIT)

After accessing the scientific researches and previous studies which has used similar educational programs close to the current program such as the Low et al. (2001), Masarrat (2016) and Onezat (2006) studies, through depending on theoretical basis related to the multiple intelligences theory of Gardner which are based on a set of intelligences (linguistic, logical and spatial) with regard to the communication skills, its education and procedural components, the researchers have constructed an educational program which includes activities, exercises and have a general content containing a group of letters, syllables, words, sentences, pictures, and

paragraphs. The training activities concentrated on the strategies and methods of every intelligence in the multiple intelligences determined in the current study to promote and develop communication skills and integration between listening, conversation, reading and writing skills. The gradient in activities was from simple to composite, or from easy to difficult until the child attained mastery addition, it used the methods of praise and reinforcement when reacting to correct answers to ensure their effectiveness and interaction with the activities of the program. Furthermore, the program activities have been applied by the female teachers at kindergarten after training and preparing them by introducing them to the program, its methods, strategies, and how to implement and write the individual educational plans based on multiple intelligences.

Program Arbitration

The suggested educational program was presented to a group of arbitrators to know their views of the following aspects: how well is the program based to the multiple intelligences theory and its components, how true is the program to its components, and the what is the way those components are viewed and sequenced, the soundness of the draft, formulation the educational purposes of the program, the soundness of trainings and skills in terms of the accuracy of linking the knowledge with the application in the program, the schedule to the program's application, and the appropriateness of the program skills and activities to its goals. Moreover, does the program meet the actual needs of the targeted category enhancing the performance level, flexibility and other multiple choices which allow various activities that are consistent with the tendencies, desires, and trends etc. were the other recommendations and amendments by arbitrators that were taken into consideration.

Procedures

1. The educational material was selected from the Arabic language subject of second level kindergarten.
2. Design and production of the educational content of the suggested program and identifying the goals of the educational course based on the multiple intelligences, after presenting them to a set of arbitrators.
3. Application of the pre-academic achievement test on the two groups (control and experimental) and checking the validity and reliability of the material, in cooperation with the female teachers.
4. Meeting the female teachers who will teach the subject to the two groups (control and experimental), to agree on the number of teaching classes of the unit subjects, to achieve parity in the number of classes through procedural framework which includes guidance and instructions related to the mechanism of implementation of the lesson, training them to utilize the suggested educational program to teach the selected educational material and a suggested time plan to implement it, along with the plans for preparing lessons.
5. Starting to apply the suggested educational program on the experimental group in which it has continued for eight weeks.
6. Applying the academic achievement test after finishing with the teaching.
7. Six weeks after the trial ended, the academic achievement test was applied to measure the learning influence maintenance caused by the study program.

Findings and Discussion

First question: What is the influence of the suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory on developing communication skills (listening, conversation, reading and writing) for the students of kindergarten (KG2)?

Table 3: Means and standard deviations of the student's responses in the two study groups on the test of development of communication skills

Test	Group	Sample size	Pre-test		Post-test	
			Mean	Standard Deviation	Mean	Standard Deviation
Communication skills development	Control	185	63.9	10.8	65.5	10.7
	Experimental	185	64.6	10.7	75.3	10.7

From the findings, it is observed that there are virtual differences in means of the student's responses on the post-test of development of communication skills, in which mean of the control group was (65.5), while mean of the experimental group was (75.3).

And to check the influence of using the suggested educational program a ONE WAY ANCOVA test was conducted and Table (4) explains the findings of this analysis.

Table 4: The findings of variance analysis (ANCOVA)

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Suggested educational program	7720.212	1	7720.212	468.512	0.000*
Pre-test	36125.991	1	36125.991	2192.35	0.072
Error	6047.48	367	16.478		
Total	1885030	370			

It is observed from the results that (F) value of the suggested educational program in educating the experimental group was (468.512), the significance level of it was (0.000) and it has statistical significance of ($\alpha=0.05$), which indicates that there are statistical differences among student's responses on the test on the development of communication skills because of using the program. This result confirms the effectiveness of the suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in developing communication skills.

This is because the multiple intelligences theory seeks to utilize the knowledge processes and deepening them for the students in constructing the concepts, meanings, words, pictures and images, and their mathematical, logical, spatial and linguistic significances in addition to create a learning environment which encourages them to be active participants in the learning process, so as Afanah and Al-Khazendar (2007) indicated that multiple intelligences and their differences among the learners requires following various learning educational approaches to achieve the communication skills to all learners in the classroom. Moreover, the current educational program allowed students to diversify the spatial, optical, mathematical, logical, verbal, linguistic and thinking approaches and to address the available information in their knowledge construction in many ways that are convenient to the common intelligence's patterns for them in this age.

Perhaps one of things that contributed in enhancing the student's results in the post-achievement test of the communication skills (listening, conversation, reading and writing) in this study is the concentration of the program on many different learning sources and activities taking into consideration the individual differences between them and the learning patterns practiced by the students in their daily life and then re-forming and putting them in an educational framework contained in the content of listening, conversation, reading and writing in accordance with every type of the intelligences types specified in the current study. This study's results along with the results indicated by many other studies have confirmed the positive influence of the program based on the multiple intelligences theory on the students' achievement, their success and maintenance of learning influence (Al-Zoubi, 2020; Masarrat, 2016; Awad, 2011; Al-Ahdal, 2009; Bilgin, 2006; Onezat, 2006; Saleh, 2004; Davis, 2004; Low et al, 2001).

Second question: What is the influence of using the suggested educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in retention of learning for the students of kindergarten (KG2)? In order to check the retention of learning influence as a result of using the program, ANCOVA has conducted (8) weeks after the trial ended. Table (5) illustrates the results of this analysis.

Table 5: The results of the variance analysis (ANCOVA) after (8) weeks

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Suggested program	48.628	1	48.628	5.597	0.000*
Pre-test	52.669	1	52.669	6.062	0.018
Error	399.671	46	8.689		
Total	13159.0	49			

From the findings have been mentioned above, it is observed that (F) value of using the educational program in teaching the experimental study group was (5.597), its significance level was (0.000) and it has statistical significance of ($\alpha=0.05$). It indicates the existence of differences with a statistical significance among student's responses on the test of development of the communication skills because of using the program, which confirms the retention of learning as a result of using the educational program in teaching the experimental group.

The researchers attribute this result to the fact that the suggested program contributed in increasing the motivation of the students to learn through making the learning material more interesting and exciting for them. Moreover, this indicates the ability of the suggested study program to convert the vocabulary in the prescribed units in the current study into meaningful learning, linked to the previous learning of the students, so that it maintains a greater influence in their minds making it easy to remember and difficult to forget. Furthermore, the activities followed in the program keeps the students as the axis and focus of learning, as a result, they themselves could access a lot of concepts related to the communication skills as a result of which information will be maintained for a long time and it differs information acquired by them using traditional ways of learning such as memorization for instance, since this can be easily forgotten. In addition, the current study results agree with regard to the effectiveness of utilizing the multiple intelligences theory in the educational programs and its effectiveness in the maintenance of learning influence, in addition to increase the achievement level, with the Al-Ahdal (2009) study.

Recommendations

In the light of the findings, the study recommended of the necessity of diversifying the teaching methods and using diverse educational strategies according to the diversity of the children's intelligences and their interests, tendencies and abilities. We also recommend the kindergarten curricula designer to amend the curricula in accordance with children intelligences in designing the Arabic language curriculum in particular, and other curricula in general, to diversify teaching methods.

Conclusion

The study findings have shown the effectiveness of the suggested educational program in developing communication skills (listening, conversation, reading, and writing) and in retention of learning influence for the students of experimental group as compared to the control group.

References

- Abu Maghli, S. & Salameh, A. (2005). Educating reading and writing. Amman: Dar Al-Bedaya.
- Afana, E. & Al-Khazendar, N. (2007). Classroom teaching through multiple intelligences. Amman: Dar Al-Masira for publishing and distribution.
- Afana, E. & Al-Khazendar, N. (2009). Multiple intelligence – classroom methods. Amman: Dar Al-Masira.
- Al-Ahdal, A. (2009). The effectiveness of the teaching methods and activities based on the multiple intelligences theory in enhancement the achievement of Geography and learning influence maintenance for the female students of the first secondary grade in Jeddah Governorate. *Journal of Um-Alqura University for the Educational and Psychological sciences*, 1 (1): 192-242. <http://search.mandumah.com/Record/58799>
- Al-Assaf, J. & Abu-Latifa, R. (2009). Developing language skills for kindergarten child. Amman: Arab society library.
- Al-Esawi, J.; Musa, M. & Al-Sherawi, A. (2005). Arabic language teaching methods in the stage of primary education. Al-Ain: University book house.
- Al-Khaffaf, E. (2011). Multiple intelligences applied program. Edition 1. Amman: Curricula House.
- Al-Salti, N. (2004). Learning based on the brain. Amman: Dar Al-Masera.
- Al-Tahhan, T. (2003). Readiness skills for reading in the early childhood. Amman: Dar Al-Fikr.
- Al-Waqfi, R. (2003). Introduction to learning difficulties: theory and application. Jordan: Publications of Princess Tharwat college.
- Al-Zoubi, N. (2020). The influence of training program on the Gardener theory of different intelligences in developing the verbal and linguistic skills and its reflection on the performance of students with learning difficulties. *Journal of Islamic University for Educational and Psychological Studies*, 28 (3): 172-197. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.33976/iugjeps.v28i3.5576>
- Armstrong, T. (2006). Multiple intelligences in the classroom. (Translated by National Schools of Al-Dhahran). KSA, Educational Book House.
- Awad, A. (2011). The effect of using teaching strategy based on the multiple intelligences theory in attainment the physical concept for the tenth-grade students. *Dirasat, educational sciences*, 1(38): 76-93. <https://journals.ju.edu.jo/DirasatEdu/article/viewFile/2366/2244>
- Bilgin, Elmas K. (2006). The Effect of Multiple Intelligences Based Instruction on Ninth Grades Chemistry Achievement and Attitudes Toward Chemistry. Unpublished Master's thesis. Middle East Technical University Ankara. <https://etd.lib.metu.edu.tr/upload/12607413/index.pdf>
- Davis, Linda. (2004). Using the Theory of Multiple Intelligences to Increase the Fourth Grade Student's Academic Achievement in Science. Unpublished PhD dissertation. Nova Southeastern University, USA. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED491477>
- Gardener, H. (1983). *Frames of Mind*. USA: Fontana Press.
- Gardener, H. (1993). *Multiple Intelligences, the Theory in Practice*. New York, Basic Books.
- Hussein, A. (2003). Measurement and assessment of the abilities of multiple intelligences. Amman: Thought House.
- Jaber, A. (2003). Multiple intelligences and understanding, development and deepening. Cairo: Arab Thought House.
- Karen, G. (2010). Multiple Intelligences Theory: A Framework for Personalizing Science Curricula. *Journal of School Science and Mathematics*, 4 (101): 3-14. DOI: [10.1111/j.1949-8594.2001.tb18021.x](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1949-8594.2001.tb18021.x)
- Low, K. Nelson, A. Donnell, K & Walker, M. (2001). Improving reading skills. ERIC Documents Reproduction Service. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED456414.pdf>
- Masarrat, M. (2016). The effectiveness of educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in developing the achievement and mathematical thought and the maintenance of learning influence for the high primary stage students in Jordan. *Al-Azhar University, Journal of education*, 171: 622- 642. DOI: 10.21608/JSREP.2016.49068
- Murad, O. (2021a). Multiple Intelligences in Light of Gardener's Rating and the Extent of their Consistency with Academic Disciplines for the Students of Al-Balqa Applied University. *Universal Journal of Education*, 9(2): 350-361. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2021.090211.
- Murad, O. (2021b). Effectiveness of a Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy Program on Reducing Psychological Stress and Improving Achievement Motivation among University Students. *Universal Journal of Education*, 9(6): 1316-1322. DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2021.090621

- Murad, O. (2018). The ability of (linguistic and mathematical) multiple intelligence in predicting the achievement of higher primary stage students in Jordan in the courses of Arabic and Math. Proceeding of the 4th International Conference on Education, Bangkok, Thailand, 4 (2): 96-104. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.17501/24246700.2018.4212>
- Mubaideen, S. (2003). Education of reading and writing for children. Amman: Arab thought house.
- Naser, H. & Al-Abbadi, H. (2005). The influence of role-playing strategy in developing speech skill for the third primary grade. Jordanian journal in educational sciences, 1 (1): 51-65. <https://search.emarefa.net/detail/BIM-291758>
- Onezat, Sabah. (2006). The effectiveness of educational program based on the multiple intelligences theory in enhancement the skills of reading and writing for the students with learning difficulties. Unpublished Master's thesis. Arab Amman university for post-graduate studies, Jordan. <https://search.emarefa.net/detail/BIM-423559>
- Saleh, M. (2004). Multiple intelligences theory as an approach to develop mathematical logical intelligence and optical/ spatial intelligence for the kindergarten children. Journal of Educational Research, 3(2), 64-109. <https://search.mandumah.com/Record/3173>
- Tuaimah, R. & Manna, M. (2001). Teaching Arabic in general learning: theories and experiences. Cairo: Dar Al-Fikr Al-Arabi.

Author Information

Odeh Suleiman Murad*

Al-Balqa Applied University- Al-Shoubak
University College
P. O .Box (5) Al-Shoubak –71911 – Jordan

Raed Ahmad Al-Kriemeen**

Al-Balqa Applied University- Salt College Of
Humanities
Salt-Jordan

Walled Mohammad Al-Shatarat

Al-Balqa Applied University- Salt College Of
Humanities
Salt-Jordan
